

Project info

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Version history

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Statement of Originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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1 Executive Summary

200SMEChallenge Project aims to demonstrate the added value of the co-creation process to improve UX - User Experience in digital applications for companies. This objective was achieved through the “Challenge” open innovation concept (a.k.a. innovation contest): a set of multidisciplinary teams formed by students from different entities such as universities, design institutes, etc. that have in common the ability of providing ideas, suggestions about how to improve the usability of user interface of digital applications (a.k.a apps) from target SME companies.

The Project has been implemented by 7 European partners: Hub Innovazione Trentino (Italy), Espaitec Science and Technology Park (Spain), Business Oulu (Finland), Steinbeis- Europa Zentrum (Germany), Dansk Design Centre (Denmark), Tehnopol (Estonia), and Lithuanian Innovation Center (Lithuania).

As one of the project deliverables, each partner has organized local UX Challenges in which a common methodology, defined in advance by Hub Innovazione Trentino (based indeed on the Design Sprint method), has been piloted and validated together with solvers, testers and target SME companies during the competition. The main project deliverable (D2.2 Practical Guide for Innovation Agencies to adopt and scale up the scheme) has enriched, thanks to the lessons learned in the different pilots implemented in each country, the original methodology designed by Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) used in previous projects of the same nature.

Overall, the UX Challenge can be considered a tool to improve digital products and services usability (current and new developments) by means of co-design, no-coding co-implementation and rapid prototyping involving a triad formed by students from different entities (universities, Design Institutes and similar profiles) as solvers of UX companies challenges, testers (final users that will validate the solutions proposed) and target SME companies the ones that will pose the correspondent UX Challenges to the solvers.

Beyond that, the process has facilitated the capacity building of the participants in several aspects such as collaborative technology tools (Miro, Slack, Zoom, ...) and soft skills: team working, leadership, cooperativeness, communication skills, etc.

This deliverable includes the report of the 7 UX Challenges that were held in the seven partnering countries. Along with the reports, the main results and outcomes are reports, along with feedback from the partners piloting the UX Challenges. This deliverable is designed to provide comprehensive information about how each of the seven UX Challenge was executed.

The deliverable is organized in three main sections. Section one collects the seven reports from the seven UX Challenges, separately, at a partner level. This section contains detailed in-depth information about each Challenge outcomes, impacts, along with suggestions for improvements and ideas for scaling up the scheme formulated by each partner. Section two provides a cross-cutting summary of the partner’s suggestions on how to improve and scale up the UX Challenge scheme, clustered at a topic level (not at a partner level). Finally, section three includes further suggestions on how to scale up the UX Challenge scheme to other domains, as a result of a consultation with other innovation agencies.

2 Reports from the 7 national UX Challenge

2.1 Business Oulu

2.1.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	BusinessOulu
Referent person	Pirjo Koskiniemi, Hannu Hiltunen
UX Challenge date	16-18. February
Duration (days)	2,5
Location	Remote
Number of participating companies	8
Number of solvers	36
Number of mentors	7
Number of testers	5
Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)	

<p>Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)</p>	<p>One-to-one discussions with the mentors (aims, roles, methods, schedule, expertise)</p>
<p>For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)</p>	<p>Yes / no / other NO</p>
<p>Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members</p>	<p>100 euros voucher for solvers</p>
<p>Method used to evaluate the teams</p>	
<p>Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable pictures from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).</p>	

<p>Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable snapshots of outputs of the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).</p>	

2.1.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<p>We were in contact by phone with the participating companies. All companies were very pleased with the event.</p>
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results, do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example, in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<p>Feedback from students regarding the event and how it was organized was overwhelmingly positive. They seemed to appreciate and enjoy the testing phase of the event, as it allowed them to get valuable feedback from their products’ intended audience. Students were also pleasantly surprised by how quick they were able to innovate fresh ideas and solutions for their respected company cases. Not unlike students, company representatives were also vocal to join the conversation and share their positive feedback. Companies have learned more about the design sprint method and how it can contribute to the development of their product.</p>
<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<p>We were in contact with the companies immediately after the sprint, at that time the companies did not yet know what to do next</p> <p>We don't know yet. But later when we contact these companies we will ask.</p>

<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<p>We have no evidence, but we strongly believe that this will happen</p>
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2.1.3 IMPROVEMENT

In the following table conclusions of the implementation of the local UX Challenge are detailed, including our own experience as organizers, and feedback from companies, mentors and solver . While adding bullet points, you might want to consider, amongst others, these aspects:

1. Used methodology: the design sprint
2. Solver’s profile, preparation, attitude, commitment
3. Teams performance and quality of results
4. Company background, preparation/awareness and commitment
5. Mentor’s background and commitment
6. Technical / logistical setup (Miro, Zoom, etc.)
7. Final event (duration, contents, keynotes, format)
8. Overall format and duration of the Challenge
9. ..other.

<p>1. Things that went well (to keep)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Despite the fact that the event had to be organized as an online event, it went very smoothly. • Introduction to Design sprint for solvers • Teamwork • Testing • The end results presented by the teams • Call for challenges

2. Things that did not went well (to cut)

- Company recruitment: The company outreach was difficult
- Control group companies were very disappointed that they cannot take part actual sprint
- Obtaining responses to a follow-up survey

2.1.4 EXPLOITATION

1. Do you think your organization may decide to **run again** the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?

Sure, if we have a suitable project and some money. Hopefully we can hold a next event after summertime. Feedback was so positive. Design Sprints / UX Challenges will be a part of the Innovation Services in Business Oulu.

2. What would be the **key tips** you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?

Make sure that Seeker companies understand the aim of the Design Sprint / UX Challenge and that challenges are formulated well (Solvers understand easily what they are expected to solve).

3. Do you think it could be possible to **adapt the UX Challenge format** to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?

Yes. Adapted Design Sprint is also suitable for other than digital cases.

4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may **be interested** in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?

University Innovation Centres that combine research with businesses in order to develop R&D in companies.

2.2 Taltech - Tehnopol

2.2.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	Tallinn Science Park TEHNOPOL
Referent person	Kadi Villers
UX Challenge date	March 3-5, 2021
Duration (days)	3 days
Location	online
Number of participating companies	8
Number of solvers	32
Number of mentors	8
Number of testers	32

Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)

**UX CHALLENGE TALLINN 2021
 AGENDA 3-5 MARCH**

WEDNESDAY, MARCH 3

09h00 Kick-off of the UX Challenge Tallinn 2021.
 09h30 **Session with Companies and Mentors:** Mapping and Scoping of the Challenge
 11h00 **Independent Teamwork:** How Might We...
 13h00 BREAK
 14h00 **Independent Teamwork:** Ideation & Sketching
 17h00 **Session with Mentors:** Solution Selection. Quick Validation with Companies
 18h00: End of Day 1
 Independent teamwork continues for those who want.

THURSDAY, MARCH 4

09h00 **Session with Mentors:** Introduction to Prototyping & Validation
 11h00 **Independent Teamwork:** Prototyping
 13h00 BREAK
 14h00 **TESTING AND VALIDATION INTERVIEWS**
 18h00: End of Day 2
 Independent teamwork continues for those who want.

FRIDAY, MARCH 5

09h00 **Session with Mentors:** Making Sense of Testing Results
 10h00 **Independent Teamwork:** Fine-tuning the Results and Preparing Presentations
 12h00 **Session with Companies and Mentors:** Discussing the Results with Companies
 13h00 BREAK
 14h00 **FINAL PLENARY EVENT**
 16h30 End of UX Challenge

The image shows a web interface for a challenge. At the top, it says "Start here" with a colorful icon of three people. Below that is a purple bar with the text "STEP 1 - MAP THE PROBLEM". Underneath is a black bar with the text "Working with the Mentor and the Company" and a yellow "GO" button. There are four small cards with icons and text: "What is your...?", "What is your...?", "What is your...?", and "What is your...?". Below these are three large text input areas with placeholder text: "Our UX Challenge: ... (Write here your challenge)", "The world without the problem: ... (Add here one or more points)", and "Our expected output: ... (Add here one or more points)".

**Step one completed!
Well done, solvers!**

Keep working

STEP 2 - IDEATE THE SOLUTION

**Day one completed!
You're on the right track!**

Keep working 🧑‍🔬

STEP 3 - PROTOTYPE

Examples of storyboards

Put your storyboard form

**Step three completed!
You're on your path to success!** 🏆

You almost did it! 🧑‍🔬

STEP 4 - TEST

Draft your Test Protocol form

**Step 4 completed!
You're almost there!** 🧑‍🔬

STEP 5 - EVALUATE

Put your usability Prototype form

STEP 6 - REFLECT

Reflect on the day and transfer your learnings

**Day two completed!
You're almost there!** 🧑‍🔬

We're almost done 🥳

STEP 5 - TUNE AND DELIVER

Capture and interpret the findings 100%

Put your findings here

Link your deliverables here

Design Sprint completed! You are a star! ⭐

<p>Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)</p>	<p>Phone calls with companies; 2 Solvers' Orientation Sessions (online), 2 Mentors' Orientation Sessions (online)</p>
<p>For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members</p>	<div data-bbox="594 659 1419 1121" data-label="Image"> <p>The image is a presentation slide titled "Prizes". It features a central graphic of a podium with three silhouettes of people standing on it. Above the podium, there is a logo for "KULD MUNA '21" which consists of a yellow egg on a black background. To the left and right of the podium are three identical photos of a group of people in a meeting, each with the caption "Meeting with 3 top Estonian design agencies".</p> </div> <p>Kuldmuna '21 = tickets to all team members to Golden Egg Gala Golden Egg is an annual awards event and festival for design, advertising and creative agencies</p>

<p>Method used to evaluate the teams</p>	<p>Each jury member gave grades from 1 to 5 for each team for the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality of the results (do they correspond to the initial task? Do they solve the problem?) - Applicability of the solution - Innovativeness and novelty of the solution - Integrity of the solution (does it need further development?) - Clarity and quality of the presentation - Work done in 3 days (what did the team achieve during that time)? <p>The jury consisted of the 8 Mentors (who all are design experts and professionals). None of the Mentors were allowed to assess their own team - so each jury members gave grades to 7 teams only.</p> <hr/> <p>UX CHALLENGE TALLINN 2021 - FINAL PRESENTATIONS 05.01.2021</p> <p>Hea ZÜRRIIGE Fred!</p> <p>Palun lisa oma hinnad 5-palli skaalal alla tabelisse iga esitluse kohta selle tšimi lõpetamise hetkel (1 = kõige nõrgem ning 5 = kõige tugevam hinn). Palun lisa seda reaalejaes jooksvalt igat esitlust kuulata või kohe pärast selle lõppu - et anda mulje ja tulemus väikelt meele oleks ja teiste esitluste omadega hiljem segi ei läheks ning et saaksite koostulemusel küsitleda peale viimase esitluse lõppu kõikide kogurõõmide viilid välja selgitada. Peale viimase esitluse lõppu on Sul aega 5 min, et teha panud hinnetesse parandusi või teha tühjad lüngad - siis läheb hindamisvorm lukku.</p> <p>Hindamiskriteeriumideks on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tulemuse kvaliteet (kas vastavad sihtteesedele? Kas lahendavad probleemid?) - Tulemuse rakendatavus - Tulemuse innovaatilisus ja uuendus - Tulemuse terviklikkus (kas vajavad veel lisatööd?) - Esitluse selgus ja kvaliteet - Tähtsus töö 3 päeva jooksul (mida jõudis tšim saavutada selle aja jooksul?) <p>Hinnad tulemuste ja võitjate hindamiseks</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>TİM 1 CODERHYTHM</th> <th>TİM 2 BRIS</th> <th>TİM 3 MYPLAN</th> <th>TİM 4 MYSPOITIT</th> <th>TİM 5 BOIM</th> <th>TİM 6 LABITOWELLNESS</th> <th>TİM 7 TURNIT</th> <th>TİM 8 JEPSENT</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Tulemuse kvaliteet</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> <td>3</td> <td>5</td> <td>4</td> <td>4</td> <td>4</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tulemuse rakendatavus</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> <td>3</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tulemuse innovaatilisus</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> <td>3</td> <td>3</td> <td>2</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tulemuse terviklikkus</td> <td>4</td> <td></td> <td>3</td> <td>5</td> <td>4</td> <td>4</td> <td>3</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Esitluse selgus</td> <td>3</td> <td></td> <td>2</td> <td>5</td> <td>3</td> <td>5</td> <td>3</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Tähtsus töö</td> <td>5</td> <td></td> <td>3</td> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> <td>4</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Oma tšimi arvu hindad</i></p>		TİM 1 CODERHYTHM	TİM 2 BRIS	TİM 3 MYPLAN	TİM 4 MYSPOITIT	TİM 5 BOIM	TİM 6 LABITOWELLNESS	TİM 7 TURNIT	TİM 8 JEPSENT	Tulemuse kvaliteet	3		3	5	4	4	4	4	Tulemuse rakendatavus	4		5	5	5	5	3	5	Tulemuse innovaatilisus	4		2	3	3	3	2	3	Tulemuse terviklikkus	4		3	5	4	4	3	3	Esitluse selgus	3		2	5	3	5	3	4	Tähtsus töö	5		3	5	5	5	5	4
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<p>Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)</p>	<p>All Testers got a 30 eur voucher for Rahva Raamat bookstore (they have online store as well)</p>																																																															

Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable **pictures** from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

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Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable **snapshots** of outputs of the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).

2.2.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<p>Companies gave their feedback in a 1 min time slot in the Final Event after the team’s pitching.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All of them were very happy and satisfied with the prototypes: design, functionality and some added ideas by the Solvers that had not been thought of internally in the companies. • They also brought out that the Solvers understood their products and customers’ needs very well. • Also, that the amount of work done in that short time has been surprising for them.
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example, in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<p>Companies have said:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation triggered a lot of interesting and useful discussions internally in our own team about how we want this product to develop, look and work like so this will be very beneficial in our further work. • The team has brought extra value to the product with new and external insights. • This format has forced us to prioritize and focus on the most relevant part/chunk of the problem to actually get it solved.

<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<p>One company clearly stated that their focus in product development has always been on technology and therefore usability has always been on the second position. Participation in the UX Challenge has opened their eyes and shifted their focus from developing technological advances to better user experience.</p> <p>About half of the companies will continue with more customer testings.</p> <p>Two companies have proposed the teams an opportunity to collaborate further in the future.</p>
<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<p>Most companies have mentioned that they have been positively surprised at working experience with student teams so they might consider that kind of collaboration more in the future.</p>

2.2.3 IMPROVEMENT

<p>1. Things that went well (to keep)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The duration of 3 days - not too short, not too long • Giving the freedom to teams to choose teamwork online channel for themselves and not scheduling and administrating the calls/meeting from the organiser side • Running 2 orientation sessions (=briefing sessions) both for Mentors and for Solvers • Using sharewell.com platform for finding and recruiting the final missing Testers • Miro board to structure and guide the work process to maximise the results in a very short timeframe • Using Slack to communicate with Mentors - very operative and fast • Good mix of participants - students mixed with more experienced designers (at least one experienced designer in each team, acts as a Mentor a bit sometimes as well)

2. Things that did not went well (to cut)

- Large dropout in Solvers' recruitment
- Networking and socializing in online format is very complicated and did not work
- RCT did not select the companies with the highest scores
- A few companies struggled with allocating enough time and/or company representatives into this project and the teams did not feel their dedication to participation

3. Suggestions for improvement (to try)

- More help and pre-work with problem scoping could be done before the actual event
- More than one team solving a company's challenge could create a kind of competitive aspect, plus offer a choice of solutions to the company
- Not use RCT in the process - harder to manage expectations, creates confusion and misunderstandings and additional work for companies (surveys)
- Prizes given out by companies - more motivation for participants and support for recruiting of Solvers
- Run an Orientation session for the companies as well (to manage expectations, increase commitment, help with problem scoping etc)

2.2.4 EXPLOITATION

<p>1. Do you think your organization may decide to run again the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?</p>
<p>Yes, as the value for the participants - both companies and Solvers - got proven and based on the feedback of companies and Mentors, there clearly is need in the market for UX-related services and awareness. The aspect that needs sorting out prior to that is the financing part - who will pay for the organisation of that? Could be the companies but</p>
<p>2. What would be the key tips you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?</p>
<p>Recruit the best companies and challenges (with the highest scores). Don't recruit students only as Solvers but other design and UX enthusiasts as well. If possible, run the event as physical event to allow socializing and networking as an additional value of the event. Increase the number of Testers and user testing interviews, if possible - that is the most valuable part in the process.</p>
<p>3. Do you think it could be possible to adapt the UX Challenge format to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?</p>
<p>Yes, I do. I see this as a problem solving methodology and the problem can be anything else than a digital product or service. I think this methodology is very adaptable to different problems, industries and company types.</p>
<p>4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?</p>
<p>Universities, Estonian Employers' Confederation, other organisations offering business support services to companies (Ülemiste City, Mektory Innovation Centre etc).</p>
<p>5. How do you think as a consortium we could facilitate and accelerate the adoption of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?</p>

With our hands-on experience we could act as advisors to those who plan to run the initiative for the first time.

2.3 Lithuanian Innovation Centre

2.3.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	Public Institution Lithuanian Innovation Centre
Referent person	Vitalija Kolisova
UX Challenge date	2021-02-18–2021-02-19
Duration (days)	2
Location	Online (Vilnius, Lithuania)
Number of participating companies	8
Number of solvers	30
Number of mentors	4
Number of testers	8

<p>Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)</p>	
<p>Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)</p>	<p>1 training session for solvers 1 call with mentors 8 separate calls with companies</p>
<p>For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members</p>	<p>The winning team (every member of the team) received a front-end programming course for beginners from the partner CodeAcademy. Once company has decided to award a bonus of 200 EUR for each participant of the team it worked with.</p>

<p>Method used to evaluate the teams</p>	<p>Companies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential impact of the results to the company (score 1 – 5) 2. Feasibility of the results (score 1 – 5) <p>Mentors per team:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ability to successfully carry out activities (score 1-5) 2. Teamwork (score 1-5) <p>Mentors as a jury:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Innovativeness of the results produced (score 1-10) 2. Completeness of the results produced (score 1-10)
<p>Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)</p>	<p>Yes, every tester received a 50€ amazon voucher</p>

Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable **pictures** from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable **snapshots** of outputs of the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).

2.3.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<p>Companies have been generally impressed with the results provided by the solvers. At least three companies have decided to work on those results further. One of them said that they will program the results provided by the solvers into their app.</p>
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results, do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<p>Companies were impressed by the abilities of some solver teams and decided to further work with them in order to develop solutions provided during the UX Challenge. Companies have also learned more about the design sprint method and how it can contribute to the development of their product.</p>
<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<p>Yes. At least three companies have expressed their interest on further developing a solution obtained during the UX Challenge. Two of those companies have even decided to work with the same team of solvers from the UX Challenge. One of those companies has decided to award a bonus of 200 EUR for each participant of the team it worked with. Other companies have said that the ideas and solutions provided by the solvers will be taken into consideration but have not specified to what extent.</p>
<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<p>Three companies that have decided to continue developing solutions provided during the UX Challenge will improve their digital products and might even employ some of the solvers they continue working with. Others might consider similar brainstorming activities in the future or would gladly participate in similar initiatives.</p>

2.3.3 IMPROVEMENT

1. Things that went well (to keep)

- Introduction to Design sprint for solvers
- Teamwork
- Contribution and assistance by the mentors to teams
- Testing
- The end results presented by the teams
- Main prize/award for the winning team
- Call for challenges
- Call for solvers
- Call for testers
- Interaction with mentors
- Partnership with the institution providing young UI/UX specialists

2. Things that did not went well (to cut)

- Technical issues (starting from the variation of links that have been distributed to different participants of the UX Challenge, continuing with the ability to read and share information on a platform used for the UX Challenge and finishing with going live on social media from the platform used). Maybe a different platform was needed. Maybe more testing with different people could solve some of these issues.
- The RTC part of the selection process. The majority of companies did not get the random selection of the challenges for the UX Challenge. This whole experiment side of the UX Challenge made it harder to get companies interested to participate and later provide their input. What is more, due to random nature of selection, not all the companies selected were the best ones to take part in the UX Challenge and therefore could appreciate its benefits to the fullest;
- Distribution of responsibilities among local partners involved in the organisation of UX Challenge. Any misunderstanding there leads to complications during the UX Challenge. What is more, it is hard to control partners if they do not perform certain responsibilities and this creates additional problems during the UX Challenge instead of reducing the number of them;
- Not enough time for ideation and prototyping. Both solvers and companies have expressed their willingness to have more time for the development of solutions. Solvers

did not have enough time to come up with nearly final versions of the product whereas companies felt that with more time the results might have been even more impressive.

3. Suggestions for improvement (to try)

- Better communication with all parties involved (starting with local partners, continuing with the UX Challenge participants and finishing with the communication and organisation of the final event). None of the parties involved have read call for application documents, so all the information provided in those documents should be transferred into a verbal information during training sessions or meetings with companies, testers and mentors)
- Testing all technical aspects of the UX Challenge and final event with different possible scenarios that may occur during the real event.
- Even though all solvers have been contacted one or two days before the event and have confirmed their participation, there was still a significant dropout during the event. This might be due to the challenges that solvers were assigned (we have not allowed solvers to choose challenges they would like work on) on the day of the UX Challenge. However, in order to allow solvers to choose challenges, more solvers should apply for the event.
- Some companies needed a very detail explanation on how to present the challenge and what results they might expect at the end of the event. Thus, on one hand, companies need a separate training on what a UX challenge or design sprint are, on the other hand, choosing companies by the soundness of their application instead of randomly, could solve this issue itself.
- For some teams, giving a freedom of what programs and software to use while implementing the UX Challenge was an advantage, for others it was a drawback as they felt a bit lost among the options. So maybe, it is good to provide a recommended framework, but leave it open for other teams to choose another direction.

2.3.4 EXPLOITATION

1. Do you think your organization may decide to **run again** the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?

After seeing the result (3 companies have decided to adapt the solution from the UX Challenge to their products) we might consider offering the UX Challenge-like initiatives in the future. However, to do that we would need to attract additional funding as the organisation of the initiative requires financial, human and time resources that we do not have outside of the scope of 200SMEchallenge project.

2. What would be the **key tips** you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?

- Assign more days to the UX Challenge itself, regardless of the format (we had a two-day event). The one thing that solvers and companies have had in common in terms of the comments is that the UX Challenge was too short and they would like more time to work on ideas and prototyping.
- Also, companies would like to be more involved in the whole event and have similar training about the design sprint as the solvers had.
- Make sure to avoid technical issues, especially if event is organised online. Test as much as possible platforms and especially their switches to live events on social media platforms in order to avoid misunderstandings and time breaks. It is good to bring third party people to test breakout rooms, ability to share documents etc.
- Provide as much information as possible to all participants involved in advance. It is a time-consuming task, but might help to avoid some misunderstanding during the event. For instance, there was one team that started looking for their own testers even though testers would be provided to the team by the organisers. However, somehow this information was not communicated clearly enough before the event. Some companies have been also lost during the event as they could not find the right link to join the meeting with their team. This happened because companies received several different links (one for the beginning of the UX Challenge, the other to join their team, the third one was for the final event). There might be less misunderstandings with live events, however, once it is organised online and there are breakout sessions planned etc. more attention to detail is necessary and more time to communicate this information to all participants.
- Try to look for the partners that can help to attract solvers, testers and mentors to the event.
- Also, look for sponsors to get valuable prizes for the winners and other participants.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide certificates to the solvers as they would like to add them to their portfolios.
<p>3. Do you think it could be possible to adapt the UX Challenge format to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?</p>
<p>Yes, it is possible. Design sprint can be applied beyond digital challenges. It could be very useful for some social challenges, for NGO sector and social enterprises. We actually received several requests from NGO and even public sector (like public companies) and had to decline then even though their challenge would be perfect with the design sprint methodology.</p>
<p>4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Innovation Hubs; • Clusters; • Business support organizations; • Universities or other institutions providing technical skills to future UI/UX specialists • Public Innovation Agencies • NGO sector
<p>5. How do you think a as a consortium we could facilitate and accelerate the adoption of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage with Innovation agencies possibly interested in the topic. • Demonstrate the benefits of the event by using the feedback from solvers and companies while presenting the UX Challenge; • Think about the international scope of the UX Challenge, for challenges, solvers, mentors, testers (maybe it could be organised as a multinational event instead of region-based).

2.4 Danish Design Centre

2.4.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	Danish Design Centre
Referent person	Emma Jade Wang, Project Manager
UX Challenge date	17th-19th of March 2021
Duration (days)	3 Days
Location	Online - Denmark
Number of participating companies	8
Number of solvers	30
Number of mentors	8
Number of testers	16

Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)

200 SME CHALLENGE UX Challenge - Schedule

Wednesday (17th of March)	Thursday (18th of March)	Friday (19th of March)
INTRO	INTRO	INTRO
Map the problem	Prototype	Tune results
Ideation	Break	Break
Break	Test	Results to Company (presentation)
Ideation		Plenary/Final Event
Decision		

Day 1:

200 SME CHALLENGE Todays program

Time	Activity	Involvement
8:30-8:45	Welcome to the UX Challenge	Solvers, Mentors, Companies
8:45-10:00	Phase 1: MAP THE PROBLEM (company presentations)	Solvers, Mentors, Companies
10:00-10:10	Introduction to the next Phase	Solvers, Mentors
10:10-12:00	Phase 2: Ideation (create ideas individually)	Solvers with support from Mentors
12:00-13:00	Optional Break	Solvers, Mentors
13:00-14:30	Continue Phase 2: Ideation	Solvers with support from Mentors
14:30-14:40	Introduction to the next phase	Solvers, Mentors
14:40-16:00	Phase 2: Decision	Solvers, Mentors

200 SME CHALLENGE Schedule - Day 2

Time	Activity	Participation
8:30-8:45	Welcome back	Solvers, Mentors
8:45-12:00	Phase 4: Prototyping	Solvers, Mentors
12:00-13:00	Optional Break	Solvers, Mentors
13:00-13:15	Introduction to the next phase	Solvers, Mentors
13:15-16:00	Phase 5: Testing	Solvers, Mentors, Testers

200 SME CHALLENGE Schedule - day 3

Time	Activity	Participation
8:30-8:45	Welcome back	Solvers, Mentors
8:45-12:45	Tune your results	Solvers, Mentors
12:45-13:00	Introduction to next steps	Solvers, Mentors
13:00-14:00	Presentations to Companies	Solvers, Mentors, Companies
14:15-16:00	Plenary Event	Solvers, Mentors, Companies

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

<p>Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)</p>	<p>Miro boards (screenshots): https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1sdhgp81COvDyxVDq3dRp0xwIXsCu1KZy?usp=sharing</p>
<p>For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)</p>	<p>No, we decided to not create this document. Some Solvers contacted companies directly before the UX Challenge began. This allowed them to directly ask questions + make a relevant document themselves.</p>
<p>Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members</p>	<p>Winning team (first place): UX Copenhagen Conference tickets OR 1000kr gift card Second place: Gift card = 300 kroner Third place: Gift card = 200 kroner</p>
<p>Method used to evaluate the teams</p>	<p>We sent this evaluation survey to all Solvers = https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1R_8C4VEp7zZRIbTcVWyGkltZ_iuiZrQn1yR6v7e3MTg/edit?usp=sharing</p> <p>We collected feedback from the teams: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1rT9vxTB9FZ4f3ugVTGu5FoYUnSGnOV1JD2v4-dULp2o/edit?usp=sharing</p>
<p>Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)</p>	<p>Yes, we provided all Testers with a 250kroner gift card</p>

Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable **pictures** from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

The image shows a Zoom meeting interface. The main content is a presentation slide titled "3-day Design Sprint" with the 200 SME Challenge logo. The slide features a hand-drawn diagram of the design sprint process: **Map** (with sub-points: "What are we doing?", "What are the inputs?", "Target"), **Sketch** (with sub-points: "Sketch", "Sketch", "Sketch"), **Decide** (with sub-points: "Decide", "Decide", "Decide"), **Proto-type** (with sub-points: "Prototype", "Prototype", "Prototype"), and **Test** (with sub-points: "Test", "Test", "Test"). To the right of the diagram is a book cover for "SPRINT: How to Solve Real Problems with Your Team in 3 Days". Below the slide is a Zoom control bar with icons for Mute, Stop Video, Participants, Chat, Screen Share, Remote Presentation, Raise Hand, and End.

The second screenshot shows a slide titled "User tests - who are the testers?". It includes a note: "None of the testers are customers of Legacy! = Not within beachhead segment!". Below this are three tester profiles, each with a person icon and a description:

- Tester 1** - works with day-to-day consulting, knows Legacy but has never used their services before
- Tester 2** - studies Cognition and audience engagement
- Tester 3** - has worked with finances, currently working as interaction designer. Is also average/above average age.

The slide also features a "Legacy" logo in the bottom right corner. A Zoom control bar is visible at the bottom of the slide.

See more images from the UX Challenge here:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17SwYJktaDkPyPNA5DItO8GeG5fQXhR3?usp=sharing>

Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable **snapshots** of outputs of the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).

2.4.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<p>We have received a number of comments from companies via email.</p> <p>Quotes:</p> <p>“Thank you very much for this opportunity. We were very happy with the activities, the teams and the result. Really innovative and amazing experience.”</p> <p>Translation: “the team did a great job! Could I please have their contact information? I would like to get in touch with them”.</p> <p>Translation: “We are impressed with what the students were able to produce in such a short time frame. Could you please send me their prototypes/mockups? We would like to work more with them, internally”.</p>
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results, do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example, in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<p>Some companies have maintained contact with their teams</p> <p>Companies are impressed with the Sprint method and find it useful to create solutions, fast.</p> <p>Scoping their challenge to make it very specific. Companies struggle to define the issue in a concise way. Sometimes making the challenge more complex than it is in reality.</p> <p>Mentors were able to “challenge” the views of Companies. They were able to make companies think of their products in a different way.</p>

<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<p>The UX Challenge was able to expose new potential solutions that companies did not even think about previously. It opened up for new opportunities, perspectives and new ways of thinking.</p> <p>I believe that some companies will continue working with or maintain contact with Solvers/Mentors.</p> <p>I believe that many companies will review the current version of the product and take into consideration some of the ideas/solutions developed by the Solvers.</p>
<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<p>With any type of workshop, the outcome/effect is quite short/medium term, unless the company has skills “in-house” to take it further.</p> <p>For example, Solvers have presented companies with great, valuable and realistic solutions. However, if the companies do not have competences in-house to facilitate further work and development, the output will be lower.</p> <p>That being said, based on the feedback we have received, I believe that all companies have been inspired by the “new way of working”, and have seen the benefits of a Design Sprint and the effect it can bring. This could encourage these companies to explore new ways of working in the future, to a higher extent.</p>

2.4.3 IMPROVEMENT

1. Things that went well (to keep)

- The dynamic between Mentors, Companies and Students works very well.
- Mentors bring a lot of value
- Great teamwork before the UX Challenge began
- Very proactive solvers!
- Solvers/Mentors can choose when they take breaks
- Great feedback and interaction on LinkedIn
- Introduction to each phase works very well
- Structure of the UX Challenge worked well
- ZOOM set-up very successful
- Impressive end result - the solvers were able to produce high quality, functioning prototypes. Way over expectations from us (DDC) and the companies.
- The Solvers were really great at presenting solutions
- The commitment of the Solvers was very impressive. Some chose to take no breaks, work over time etc.
- Solvers/Mentors were happy with the Miro board set-up and found it useful to help them stay on track
- Mentors were highly qualified
- Slack channel for Mentors - this allowed them to ask questions, contact Emma (DDC) directly and get fast answers
- Breakout rooms are great! You can manage the time schedule easily
- Companies were prepared with presentations etc.
- We, DDC purchased FIGMA software for all Solvers. This allowed them to create the best possible prototypes.

2. Things that did not went well (to cut)

- One company arrived 10 mins late on day 1 (map the problem).
- Solvers were concerned with the lack of breaks
- Many were “brain dead” after the end of each day
- Some issues with the breakout rooms on day 1. Participants signed onto Zoom using a different email address than the address we used to pre-define the rooms.
- Some company challenges were too broad / not UX focused
- Some companies struggled to answer the questions students had. Companies don't understand UX.
- Sometimes Solvers/Mentors forget to take breaks - become very tired
- Long days!

3. Suggestions for improvement (to try)

- Give a reason why the winners won the challenge. Spend time on an explanation
- Lack of “celebration” after the UX Challenge is complete. Would have been great to have an “after gathering” with drinks and snacks.
- There should be a mandatory evaluation for Mentors, Companies, Solvers afterwards (maybe a standard template)
- Adjust the schedule to 5 days rather than 3 days (3 days is too intense)
- Mandatory breaks would be a good idea

2.4.4 EXPLOITATION

1. Do you think your organization may decide to **run again** the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?

The UX Challenge worked very well. It definitely provided students with experience, and companies with value. Solvers were able to bring in new knowledge, methodologies and tools to the table. Definitely an initiative/method we should continue working with, also with different focus areas (not just UX).

2. What would be the **key tips** you’d give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?

Spend a lot of time on “prep-work” beforehand. Ensure everyone understands the Sprint method, and make sure to introduce the different tools and softwares beforehand. Make sure teams meet each other prior to the UX Challenge to ensure good chemistry and understanding of each other's skills. Provide teams with good software, even if this means paying for it - this allows the end result to be as good as possible.

3. Do you think it could be possible to **adapt the UX Challenge format** to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?

Yes, definitely. The UX Challenge is very flexible in a way. You can add/adjust different stages to suit the needs. For example, adding a testing phase before/after the prototype phase. The focus does not have to be UX, but something entirely different and can still be successful.

4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may actually **be interested** in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?

Unsure?

5. How do you think a as a consortium we could **facilitate and accelerate the adoption** of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?

Share the learnings of the UX Challenge in a broad context. Evaluate the outcomes for companies, the value added and the effect created.

Learn from mistakes and share “what not to do” - this is just as valuable as knowing “what to do”.

As a consortium, we should be aware of some mutual communication activities. For example, all partners share the same content, on their individual platforms. This means we are sending out the same message to different audiences.

2.5 Steinbeis Europa Zentrum

2.5.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum
Referent person	Miriam Mohr
UX Challenge date	10.-12.03.2021
Duration (days)	2.5 days
Location	Online (Karlsruhe, Germany)
Number of participating companies	8
Number of solvers	49
Number of mentors	8
Number of testers	32
Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)	

Mural Canvas

UX CHALLENGE - DEUTSCHLAND

Team Nr.
Teamleiter:

Welcome!

RESOURCES

LUX Challenge : Schedule

	10.03.	11.03.	12.03.
9:00-11:00	TEAMWORK	User Testing	
11:00-13:00	TEAMWORK	User Testing	
14:00-16:00	Pause	Pause	TEAMWORK
16:00-17:30	Team Building Sharing Goals Private	TEAMWORK	Presentation der Ergebnisse an Firmen
17:30-19:30	TEAMWORK		Picking in Plenum

Link to your Zoom private room :

Your Google shared folder :
 This folder is shared with your team mates, the company, the mentors, and the organizers. Do not share this folder further.
 In this folder you will:

- Find all the documents you need to get started:**
 - Challenge brief (short googledoc)
 - Company's Application Form to the UX Challenge (Pdf including in-depth info on the product and the challenge)
 - Documentation on the product (maybe)
 - Links to access the product (maybe)
- Put all the three Deliverables** as well as whatever document you will create during the UX Challenge.

Please do not use other folders due to confidential reasons.

Logos

Organizers
 Miriam Mohr
 Jacqueline Fritz
 ux-challenge@steinbeis-europa.de
 miriam.mohr@steinbeis-europa.de

Before we start...

TEAM BUILDING

Choose a team name!

Who is part of the team?

Team 1

1. Name

2. Members

Team 2

1. Name

2. Members

Team 3

1. Name

2. Members

Team 4

1. Name

2. Members

Team 5

1. Name

2. Members

Team 6

1. Name

2. Members

Day

Day 1: 10.03.

MAP THE PROBLEM

Kickoff meeting 30 min

What happened?
 How did you find out about the problem? What did you do about it? How did you feel about it? How did you solve it? How did you feel about it?

The world without the problem
 How would you feel about the world without the problem? How would you feel about the world without the problem? How would you feel about the world without the problem?

Our UX Challenge ...

The world without the problem ...

Our expected outcome ...

What happened?
 How did you find out about the problem? What did you do about it? How did you feel about it? How did you solve it? How did you feel about it?

The world without the problem
 How would you feel about the world without the problem? How would you feel about the world without the problem? How would you feel about the world without the problem?

Day 2: 11.03.

IDEATE THE SOLUTION

Sketch 1:30 min

Decide 1:30 min

What is a sketch ?
 Here are a couple of examples of Sketchy Ideas.
 They should fit in one page (e.g. A4 sheet) and be divided into three panels (e.g. three large post-its). You should also include short texts and notes to make it easier for your teammates to understand them.

Step 1: The message

- 1. Upload facts of the challenge**
 Write your 100 words in one to two paragraphs with maximum 100 words.
- 2. Analyse**
 Write your 100 words in one to two paragraphs with maximum 100 words.
- 3. Create notes**
 Write your 100 words in one to two paragraphs with maximum 100 words.

Sketches board

PROTOTYPE

Storyboarding 1:30 min

Examples of storyboards
 A Storyboard drawn on a whiteboard is hard to update.
 If you use post-its to depict each Step of the user flow, then it will be easier for you to develop the Storyboard iteratively (e.g. adding missing Steps, moving them around).

Example 1

Example 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Day 3: 12.03.

TEST

Test protocol 60min

Research questions

You test the Prototype because you want to learn something. **What do you want to learn?** Start from clarifying your research objectives (3 to 5, not too many, you won't have enough time).

Questions

How will you generate data? Will you ask questions? What will you call? Will you observe and take notes? What will you observe? Define how you will collect data.

Tasks

In order to have the user testing the Prototype or Prototype it's good practice to prepare and assign simple tasks. **Define your tasks in advance (one per objective).**

Questions

Testing is the most hectic phase of the Sprint. **THE MUST PLAN EVERYTHING MANUALLY** to avoid a complete disaster. What do you need to do and have in place to make tests happen?

TUNE AND DELIVER

Tune your solution 60min

Review your solution

Update your design (e.g. Prototype) on the basis of what you learned during the test. **Make sure you like the last version of the Prototype to be used here, so that engineers will always find the four version files.**

Prepare deliverables

It's really time to wrap up your results and prepare them into your final presentation(s). This will require preparing slides, and a Prototype demo to the company. **Make sure you start work on deliverables in time.**

Converge

It's time to converge. **We need to come up with leading new solutions now** (e.g. to start new user tests or interviews). There is just no time. Take a note and make sure you communicate that option to the company.

Record a pitch video

The pitch videos are key. Prepare an effective story, decide what video to shoot. Include pieces of tests in the video, decide who it best member of staff will present. Make tests before recording the final version. **Send the video as final!**

Draft your test protocols here

Plan your test protocol by defining in advance all the tasks you will assign to the user, what questions you'll ask, and/or what you'll observe.

All users should go through the same test protocol. Keep it simple and feasible. If possible, test the test with a friend upfront. You'll have only 4 testers and 50 mins each.

Task 1	Task 2
Objective E.g. Check whether the user understands how to use the Task for an appointment functionality.	Objective
Task description E.g. Please send a request for appointment to Doctor Reza on Monday, 22 February 2020 at 1pm.	Task description
Questions Question 1: E.g. Did you understand the meaning of the button "See doctor's schedule" ? Question 2: E.g. What was hard in completing the task ? Questions 3: ...	Questions Question 1: E.g. Did you understand the meaning of the button "See doctor's schedule" ? Question 2: E.g. What was hard in completing the task ? Questions 3: ...
Observation E.g. Observe whether the user finds the Task for an appointment button. Observe whether and where the user makes errors.	Observation

Agenda:

	10.03.21	11.03.21	12.03.21
9:00-11:00		TEAMWORK	User Testing
11:00-13:00		TEAMWORK	User Testing
		Break	Break
14:00-16:00		TEAMWORK	TEAMWORK
16:00-17:30	Team Building Briefing of teams by companies	TEAMWORK	Presentation of results to companies
17:30-19:30		TEAMWORK	Pitching in plenary

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)	2 training sessions with mentors, 8 meetings with companies
For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)	Yes, please see template below

UX CHALLENGE: Challenge Briefing Dokument

Unternehmen	
Name des Unternehmens	
URL Webseite	
Branche und kurze Beschreibung des Unternehmens	
Ansprechpartner UX Challenge: Vor- und Nachname	
Ansprechpartner UX Challenge: Kontaktdaten	
Produkt	
Name des Produkts (wenn bereits bekannt)	
Kurzbeschreibung des Produkts	
Entwicklungsstand des Produkts	
Endnutzer: wer verwendet das Produkt/ soll es verwenden?	
Kunden: wer kauft das Produkt/ soll es kaufen?	

<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <div style="background-color: #f8d7da; padding: 2px;">Challenge</div> <p>Ziele:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 2. 3. <p>Fragestellung: Wie können wir</p> <p>Erwartetes Ergebnis: Konzept/ Storyboard/ Wireframe/ klickbarer Prototyp</p> </div>	
Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members	All solvers received a 50€ amazon voucher. Winning team members were additionally given a voucher for the entrance to an amusement park, as well as a wine tasting/ networking session (sponsored by <i>accenture</i>).
Method used to evaluate the teams	Companies, mentors and expert judges (5 judges) gave scores to each team: <u>Companies:</u> 1. Potential impact of the results to the company (score 1 – 5) 2. Feasibility of the results (score 1 – 5) <u>Mentors:</u> 3. Team work (score 1 – 5) <u>Judges/ Experts:</u> 4. Innovativeness of the results (score 1 – 5) 5. Pitch: clear summary of work conducted, creativity (score 1 – 5)
Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)	No, all testers were recruited from personal networks or the companies' networks.
Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable pictures from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).	

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable **snapshots** of outputs of the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

2.5.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individual feedback from companies was generally very positive as was the initial score directly after the challenge (all companies gave very high scores) - expectations were met if not exceeded (prototypes were much more elaborate and detailed than expected)
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results, do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learnings for companies: how to improve communication and/or marketing of their product - Learnings for all participants: Importance of UX Design - companies gained insights from user testing for further product development - companies had the opportunity to connect with young talents - knowledge about Design Sprint and user testing à Many companies were not aware of the benefits of Design Sprints and the Design Sprint method
<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two companies indicated that they will definitely further utilize/ mature their prototypes (or are already in the process of doing so), the other companies did not make a definite statement yet - Most companies indicated they would review the current version of their product based on the findings from the UX Challenge - At least one company will hire a solver as a student trainee

<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No evidence, but indications that companies became more aware of the importance of UX Design - Companies considered working with students in the future as a result of their positive UX Challenge experience
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2.5.3 IMPROVEMENT

<p>1. Things that went well (to keep)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design Sprint method allowed creative cooperation of students • Team size of 6 solvers per team worked out well • Solver recruitment: applicants were from different universities and had diverse studying backgrounds • Solver attitude and commitment to the UX Challenge was extraordinary • Performance of teams and quality of results exceeded expectations of companies and jury members • Preparatory meetings with companies were central for the right formulation of the challenge • Virtual setting: Zoom breakout sessions • Mural board • We gave teams the choice to pitch live or to record a video à both worked out well • Duration of 2.5 days was remarked as positive by participants • Solvers working together in a virtual setting, even though they didn't know each other before • Mentors as the central bridge between companies and solvers: crucial role à mentors with background in innovation coaching and/or Design Sprint were important to support companies (even though they had little experience in UX Design itself) • Pitching of results in plenary
<p>2. Things that did not go well (to cut)</p>

- Companies indicated they would have liked to be more involved in the Design Sprint
- Team distribution was communicated on short notice, some solvers had special requests which resulted in last minute changes
- Drop-out rate was lower than expected leading to a high number of confirmed solvers (49) – too late to exclude participants from UX Challenge
- Diversity of companies and therefore challenges made the comparability of teams more difficult (some challenges were more challenging than others, some allowed for more creativity) à despite individual preparatory meetings with companies
- Company recruitment: At first, the company outreach was rather low, assumably due to a general unawareness of terms like UX Design, Design Sprint, UX Challenge, hackathon etc.
- Cooperation with university (UX Challenge could not be integrated into university course setting)
- 8 parallel zoom sessions did not work out as expected
- Recording of user testing in breakout sessions worked, but proved to be rather complicated
- Scoring for teams by mentors and companies (all gave high score)
- Teams would have needed a bit more time for problem framing/ understanding
- Companies would have liked recording of final event which was not planned

3. Suggestions for improvement (to try)

- Cooperation with external partners (particularly with universities) has to be initiated earlier
- If there are enough applications, allow solvers to choose the challenge they will work on (however: this makes organization and solver distribution more complicated)
- Communication/ promotion of UX Challenge: make sure to make communication on UX Challenge as accessible/ easy as possible in order to make the benefits clear for companies
- Since most companies struggled to formulate their UX challenge, preparatory meetings on the challenge brief were crucial
- Allow a bit more time in the beginning for problem framing
- Mentors should be included in the briefing sessions with companies
- Companies could be included in the UX Challenge process more (e.g. short feedback meetings with team and company throughout UX Challenge)

- Exploit the international setting more: Organize an international/ joint UX Challenge, mix participants from different countries à This could further improve the appeal to participants

2.5.4 EXPLOITATION

<p>1. Do you think your organization may decide to run again the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, however the precondition would be to have the right cooperation partners and to find financing for it. - Generally the format was very beneficial to our organization in terms of outreach to companies, company support, marketing, synergies between sectors
<p>2. What would be the key tips you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Look for local cooperation partners, especially universities à contact to students is crucial - Potentially sponsoring partners/ media partnerships - Personnel: plan manpower (staff with expertise and also supporting staff for organizational matters) - Consider virtual setting since this increases your potential participant number
<p>3. Do you think it could be possible to adapt the UX Challenge format to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, but format still needs to be well-thought-out and clearly defined in order to be communicable - Challenges should still be digital, with exceptions for sectors whose challenges might be difficult to define digitally (e.g. engineering/ building) - Challenges could be beyond UX Design (e.g. marketing, coding) - An adapted format with different innovation methods (e.g. Design Sprint, Scrum) could also be compelling since this would increase the students' learnings about these methods even further

- New perspective: support not only SMEs, but specifically social enterprises and/or NGOs/ non-profit associations
4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may actually be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?
- Business support organizations (chambers of commerce, local and regional business support) - Universities - Associations with a focus on technology transfer or business support/ cluster
5. How do you think a as a consortium we could facilitate and accelerate the adoption of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?
- Disseminate project results - Results of study will be relevant to prove that this kind of format actually brings benefits to companies and/ or students - Find international consortium/ partnership to jointly organize a similar initiative

2.6 Espaitec, Parc Científic i Tecnològic de la Universitat Jaume I.

2.6.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	Fundació General Universitat Jaume I (FUGEN)// Espaitec, Science and Technology park
Referent person	Juan Antonio Bertolín, General Manager of FUGEN/ESPAITEC
UX Challenge date	10,11 and 12 of March
Duration (days)	3 days

Location	Castellón (Spain) (online)
Number of participating companies	8
Number of solvers	30
Number of mentors	8
Number of testers	13
Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)	<p>Initiative agenda</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

<p>Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)</p>	<p>Espatec used zoom as online videoconference tool. ESPAITEC organized several online meetings with mentors’ team and solvers for sharing tools, methodology and scopes. On 5th of march, ESPAITEC organized the last online meeting with the mentors to confirm all the tasks assigned, reviewed and discussed.</p> <p>Previously, we contacted the 8 selected companies by phone and give them all the information about the UX hackathon.</p> <p>Leaving aside the meetings, basic information was sent to all the participants (companies, mentors, solvers and testers)</p>
<p>For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)</p>	<p>An example can be found in this link (At the moment this link is private, but you can ask for access to the link).</p>
<p>Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members</p>	<p>10 70€ FNAC Gift cards (First prize, 2 winning teams) 10 50€ FNAC Gift cards (Second prize, 2 winning teams) 5 30€ FNAC Gift cards (Third prize, 1 team winner) A mug with the logo of UX Challenge for all participants A set of different merchandising was distributed among all the solvers Bitcoinforme give 100€ to each member of the team Rumbodirecto invite the solvers of the team to a one afternoon sailing cruise</p>
<p>Method used to evaluate the teams</p>	<p>For evaluation process, online meeting with mentors was held. We analysed several aspects of the different solutions provided and scored them 0 ..5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Potential business impact of results · Feasibility of the results · Ability to perform the activities · Effectiveness of team work · Innovativeness of the results · Completeness of the results
<p>Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)</p>	<p>No incentives provided to testers.</p>

Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable **pictures** from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).

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Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable **snapshots** of outputs of the the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).

Look the **video example** in this [link](#) (Private at the moment, ask for access)

	Look some final presentations here (Private at the moment, ask for access)
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2.6.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<p>We have some data of companies, expressing the satisfaction of the work done in the hackathon. We contacted with all the companies after the hackathon and all of them expressed their satisfaction the experience that provided them new concepts and new ideas for the products. We can add some screenshots about the opinion of the companies that answer our own questionnaire.</p> <p>¿Has conseguido nuevas ideas que te puedan ayudar a mejorar o te hayan aportado nuevas perspectivas? 4 respuestas</p>

	<table border="1"> <caption>¿Te ha resultado interesante la experiencia?</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Rating</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>1</td> <td>25%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>3</td> <td>75%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Rating	Count	Percentage	1	0	0%	2	0	0%	3	0	0%	4	1	25%	5	3	75%
Rating	Count	Percentage																	
1	0	0%																	
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4	1	25%																	
5	3	75%																	
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results, do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<p>Companies achieved new forms of facing the problems and could discover the potential of the creative process in the hackathon with new people coming from different disciplines. Moreover, they learned new tools like Miro or slack in some cases.</p>																		
<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<p>As far as we know, at least one company offered grants to the students of its team. Furthermore, some companies told us that they are going to think about implement the results in their products, and one company told us that they are going to take some proposed to introduce them in the product.</p>																		
<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<p>Some impacts in a medium or long-term will be a better know how of the product and also a bigger economic impact, due to the improvements created. Furthermore, thanks to this experience the company can increase the market share.</p>																		

2.6.3 IMPROVEMENT

1. *Used methodology: the design sprint*

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Experience as organizers: It was a really useful methodology to start our first UX Hackathon, our perspectives were surpassed thanks to the methodology created by HIT.

Companies feedbacks: They handled the methodology in an agile and simple way. The methodology is easy to be used by companies.

Mentors' feedback: The methodology is suitable for the project, but the time in some cases could be short.

Solver's feedback: The methodology is difficult to work with companies that give the same added value for all the teams, due to some companies are really different from the others. Moreover, all the companies need to know their own challenge before start the hackathon, some company seem to have problems about define their challenge. It is a new methodology that needs more explanation and more examples in some cases.

2. Solvers profile, preparation, attitude, commitment

Experience as organizers: Solvers, in general, were very participative and had the best attitude to solve the problems, they had lot of skills to face the problems of the companies and they enjoy the experience, a big percentage of solvers want to participate in new editions. They work really hard and have good attitude during all the process.

Companies feedbacks: Companies give us a positive feedback about solvers and hackathon, they said that solvers give lots of points of view about the product and the improvements that can be done.

Mentors' feedback: Mentors highlighted the skills of the students, in fact they were really astonished about the level, they expected lower ideas and level from solvers.

Solver's feedback: They were happy about the experience and learnt how to create new ideas in a design thinking process.

3. Teams performance and quality of results

Experience as organizers: Results were great and gave possible solutions to make the products of companies bigger and better.

Companies feedbacks: All the companies thought that great ideas were discovered during the hackathon, but in some cases the companies, despite of the good results, will have complicated to implement the ideas in the products for several reasons like budgets, few personal in the company...

Mentors' feedback: The quality of the results obtained in the hackathon were very satisfactory thanks to the tasks and implication of the solvers. The results had a great level.

Solver's feedback: Despite in some cases the results could be better if they had more time, solvers were happy about the job done.

4. Company background, preparation/awareness and commitment

Experience as organizers: We invest lot of time to prepare the hackathon and we gave all the necessary information to the companies in previous interviews that we had with all the companies as well as solvers and mentors.

Companies feedbacks: All the previous job done by the organization had a good result, considering all the dynamization of the hackathon and all the instructions given were clear and direct.

Mentors' feedback: In general, everything was correct, but some mentors said that the testers provided for some companies were not the best persons to test the job done by the students.

Solver's feedback: Some solvers expressed the opinion that their company was not a good company for this kind of hackathon, due to the management of the company do not have the necessary skills to deal with this kind of process.

5. Mentor's background and commitment

Experience as organizers: The mentor that were selected for the hackathon are persons who have lot of experience in the memorization process, because all of them are members of SECOT, an NGO dedicated to help young entrepreneurship, so their experience was applied in the project and their task were essential.

Companies feedbacks: They consider the figure of the mentor as an important part to get great results, because they focus the students in the important things and give them security in the process.

Mentors' feedback: They regret that Mentors always are the figure less visible in all the process, but this figure is a fundamental part to carry out the hackathon experience.

Solver's feedback: Solvers created a special link with mentors, even in some teams they are still in contact and they created a WhatsApp group. We must bear in mind that solvers do not know each other before the hackathon.

6. Technical / logistical setup (Miro, Zoom, slack, mentimeter and google forms.)

Experience as organizers: Miro, slack and zoom worked perfectly and had great results, we need to improve the tool for evaluation, in this case we use mentimeter and it was not the ideal tool for this purpose. To collect information at the end of the hackathon we use google forms, not all of them answered the questions, but we had positive feedback.

Companies feedbacks: Some companies learned new tools thanks to hackathon and they say that were good tools for use in the future.

Mentors’ feedback: Intuitive tools and easy to learn how to use them if you do not have experience before. They appreciated the tips that were given before by the organization.

Solver’s feedback: The perception for the tools and logistic by the solvers was really good as you can see in the next image.

7. *Final event (duration, contents, keynotes, format)*

Experience as organizers: The final event was helpful to see all the work done by the 8 different teams. Moreover, the event helped us to decide the best teams according to the process of usability.

Companies feedbacks: Some company said that the result of the hackathon was really useful for them and they do not mind to use more time for this purpose. Another opinion is that the event has met the expectations, so they are happy with that however, one company said that it would be useful to have a guide and some milestones in order to facilitate the task that they need to do.

Mentors’ feedback: One mentor said that he preferred not to evaluate the presentation of his team, because he empathized with his own team and it would be hard to evaluate the team.

Solver’s feedback: The final event was too short, and they could not show all the work done during the 3 days for the company, because the time was limited and they only could show part of the job to the other teams. They asked a bit more of time for the presentation in next editions

8. Overall format and duration of the Challenge

Experience as organizers: The duration was one of the best points, because we thought in all the parts that participated in the hackathon (mentors, solvers, testers, companies, workers from Espaitec...), trying not to interfere with work and daily obligations.

Companies feedbacks: As we can see in the next image, they think that we had good management of the time, due to they could make compatible the work with the hackathon.

¿Ha sido adecuada la gestión del tiempo en las diferentes sesiones para que pudieses continuar tu jornada laboral sin entorpecer en exceso al trabajo diario?

4 respuestas

Mentors' feedback: Before the hackathon some of them told that 3 days was a big effort and too much time, after the hackathon all of them were happy with the duration of the challenge and said that was a really good experience.

Solver's feedback: in some cases, the team would need a bit more of time to reach a suitable solution, but in other cases they think that time was perfect, and the organization had a really good control of the time.

¿Ha sido adecuada la gestión del tiempo en las diferentes sesiones para que pudieses participar sin dificultad?

19 respuestas

a. Other. We present some feedbacks reflected for users and companies.
 Recommendations from solvers to other students to participate in other editions.

¿Recomendarías a otros estudiantes participar en otros hackathons de usabilidad?

19 respuestas

Evaluation of the organization made by the solvers

Evaluación de la organización:

19 respuestas

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Do you recommend participating others companies in the hackathon?

¿Recomendarías a otras empresas participar en otros hackathons de usabilidad?

4 respuestas

1. Things that went well (to keep)

- The support of the rest of partners and the methodology created by HIT. It was really useful to achieve the goal to realize the hackathon.
- The tools used for a virtual edition, except mentimeter.

2. Things that did not went well (to cut)

- The process of randomization. Some companies better than the companies selected were out of the hackathon, there are some factors that the process could not take into account.
- The mentimeter tool

3. Suggestions for improvement (to try)

- It is really difficult to justify prizes, because teams work with different companies and not all of the companies have the same skills and grade of commitment, so it will be better give a general prize and do not make differences.

2.6.4 EXPLOITATION

<p>1. Do you think your organization may decide to run again the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?</p>
<p>Yes, Espaitec is going to run a new UX Challenge. In fact, we are considering new dates to do a new UX Challenge with the SME that did not participate in this edition. Most likely, in september we will run another UX hackathon.</p>
<p>2. What would be the key tips you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?</p>
<p>Do a good preparation of the UX hackathon with clear instructions for everybody and try to select the best companies to avoid problems.</p>
<p>3. Do you think it could be possible to adapt the UX Challenge format to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?</p>
<p>Yes, indeed. All SMEs need improvements and new learning processes to be adapted to the present, so a UX Challenge is really necessary in lot of companies, regardless of the sector or the degree of innovation, because in a UX Challenge you can use different perspectives and disciplines to help your company. Besides, several people working together can get really good results.</p>
<p>4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may actually be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurships • Digital media • Digital SME • Tourism sector • Transportation sector

5. How do you think a as a consortium we could **facilitate and accelerate the adoption** of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?

Organizing more often, National UX hackatons, such as 200SME project has lead, and encouraging universities and design schools to participate. Other options are cross-country UX Hackatons, providing different set of solvers from different countries to companies to ensure the penetration on other European markets.

2.7 Hub Innovazione Trentino

2.7.1 SHORT REPORT

Topic	Short description
Partner organization	Hub Innovazione Trentino
Referent person	Nicola Doppio
UX Challenge date	15-19 February 2021
Duration (days)	5, part time
Location	Trento, Italy (online)
Number of participating companies	12
Number of solvers	65
Number of mentors	15
Number of testers	42

<p>Initiative agenda and/ or Miro Canvas (high quality screenshot)</p>	<p>The image shows two screenshots from a Miro canvas. The top screenshot is a poster for the 'FINAL EVENT' of the 'UX CHALLENGE' on 'venerdì 19 FEBBRAIO' from 14.30 to 17.00. The poster features a hand holding a smartphone and a laptop. Below the poster is a detailed agenda for the design sprint, listing activities from 14.30 to 17.00, including 'Kick-off', 'Problem Statement', 'Challenge', 'Problem Definition', 'Sprint Kick-off', 'Sprint Planning', 'Sprint Execution', and 'Sprint Review'. The bottom screenshot shows a Miro canvas with a design sprint process flow, including stages like 'Before we start...', 'Start here', 'Keep working', 'You almost did it!', and 'We're almost done!'. Each stage includes a corresponding screenshot of a website or application interface.</p>
<p>Preparatory activities (e.g. solvers training sessions; meetings with mentors; meetings with companies)</p>	<p>2 training sessions for solvers on the design sprint, which included an ice-breaking activity; phone calls with mentors and companies.</p>
<p>For every company and challenge one challenge brief page was prepared (see this template)</p>	<p>Yes</p>

<p>Prize and/or incentives provided to solvers or winning team(s) members</p>	<p>Winning team: Interaction Design Foundation one-year membership; 2nd team: 3 months access to “UIE’s all you can learn library”; 3rd team: access to the streaming of the UX Conference.</p>
<p>Method used to evaluate the teams</p>	<p>The teams were evaluated considering 1) the presentation of their results during the final event, by an external committee of experts and by the company they “worked” for; 2) the work done during the challenge week, by the mentors of each team.</p>
<p>Did you provide testers with any incentives? (e.g. Amazon vouchers)</p>	<p>30€ Amazon vouchers</p>
<p>Please include here 3-5 high quality publishable pictures from the initiative (e.g. including zoom screenshots).</p>	

Please include here 2-3 high quality publishable **snapshots** of outputs of the initiative (e.g. interface prototypes, wireframes, mockups).

2.7.2 ADDED VALUE

Topic	Your report
<p>1. OUTPUTS. Do you have any evidence about satisfaction of companies with regards of the UX Challenge outputs (interface mockup, wireframe, prototypes, insights from user testing)?</p>	<p>Overall satisfaction with the outputs, considering the time available; some companies have already started disseminating internally the outputs; 4 companies were very satisfied about the user testing phase. The outputs either confirmed hypotheses the company has already made or helped in developing new hypotheses.</p> <p>Average of 4,5 out of 5.</p>
<p>2. OTHER RESULTS. Beyond the outputs, what other results, do you think companies were able to achieve thanks to the participation in the UX Challenge? For example in terms of knowledge of new methodologies, techniques and standards; getting to know new people (networking) and organizations?</p>	<p>For almost all the companies, the networking was something very valuable but it was lost due to the online format, but it was compensated by the great interactions with the mentors and the value of having directly participated daily in the team activities. Another positive result they took with them was the knowledge and the use of new tools and techniques such as Miro boards, user testing and competitor analysis.</p> <p>Average of 4 points out of 5.</p>
<p>3. OUTCOMES. Do you have evidence about the fact that the UX Challenge will trigger, as a direct effect, new actions or interventions in the companies? For example: to industrialize or further mature the outputs of the Challenge? To review the current version of the product? To launch new projects? To follow up and launch collaborations with students (including internships or contracts), and/or mentors? To source UX design services? Training programs to internal staff?</p>	<p>Ten companies out of 11 reached out expressed the intention to implement the outputs emerged from the ux challenge, while the other one will proceed in another way (starting a collaboration with the mentor); 8 companies are thinking and moving towards the development of some kind of relationship with the students of their team (with internships or collaborations), while 3 will proceed contacting the mentors in order to start a professional collaboration with them.</p> <p>Average of 4,4 points out of 5</p>

<p>4. IMPACTS. Beyond the outputs, other results, and outcomes of the initiative, do you have evidence that the UX Challenge may produce, even indirectly, medium or long-term impacts in companies? What these could be?</p>	<p>Positive potential impacts were reported by all the companies, while they all have different starting points, which influences their capability to implement the results of the challenge or to adopt user centered methodologies (problems in company rigidity, unavailable financial means for new investments and so on).</p> <p>Average of 4,1 points out of 5.</p>
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2.7.3 IMPROVEMENT

<p>1. Things that went well (to keep)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Got the numbers • 5 days, more • Miro, followed the process • Results, satisfaction • Technical issues, we could have more (test)
<p>2. Things that did not went well (to cut)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team building • More training of the sprint (map the problem) • Preparation of videos • Networking • RCT-related <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ We had to select companies that we would have not selected (non-innovative) ○ We could not select the best companies ○ Leaving out the non-selected (other treatment after the FuS)
<p>3. Suggestions for improvement (to try)</p>

- Work better on the preparation
- Larger staff
- Blended format
- Integrate with courses
- International setting was not leveraged

2.7.4 EXPLOITATION

1. Do you think your organization may decide to **run again** the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?

Yes: we have been running the UX Challenge since 2017, and we'll keep on organizing it in the future, maybe with some **changes** in the format (e.g. duration, preparatory activities, integration with relevant university courses). Integrate with courses.

2. What would be the **key tips** you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?

1. Promotion

1. Manage the launch and promotion as you would launch an innovative product into the market: design a marketing funnel based on a stage-gate approach; manage the single applications and act on them with promo and communication actions to have them convert from prospects, to leads, to customers.
2. Leverage on partners' channels to promote the initiative

2. Preparation

1. Invest as much as possible in preparatory activities with solvers (training on the design sprint, meeting with mentors, ice breaking and team building activities)
2. Preparing the Miro boards, which needs to incorporate the template for the sprint activities
3. Invest as much as possible in preparatory activities with companies (creating a shared challenge brief document for clarifying the challenge, its constraints, the goal of the sprint, and the expected outputs)
4. Getting the product ready for the challenge: it needs to be accessible and testable by solvers and testers

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Briefing the mentors about the process and the companies and challenges selected in the initiative <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Execution <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoring progress and implementation with both solvers, mentors and companies to identify possible issues, especially in the beginning of the sprint (phase 1: Map the problem) 2. Give enough space for presenting the results, both to solvers and companies: the final event should be the celebration of a successful initiative and the value it provides to all participants 4. Follow up <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Informal phone calls with participating companies to evaluate satisfaction and outcomes 2. Use the same evaluation method across years to compare results
<p>3. Do you think it could be possible to adapt the UX Challenge format to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes: starting from the UX Challenge format, we have designed other two Innovation Challenges: one with the aim to accelerate the adoption of Additive Manufacturing in SMEs; another with the aim to accelerate the adoption of Artificial Intelligence solutions in manufacturing SMEs. They both have longer time spans than the UX Challenge (about 3 months). However, the working model is very similar: what changes is basically the problem-solving activities, and the profile of companies and solvers. • In the future we might decide to activate other Innovation Challenges in the domain of biotechnologies.
<p>4. What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities, through teams and initiatives aiming at supporting innovation and education in entrepreneurship: Contamination Labs, technology transfer offices • Open Innovation service providers in the market: offering the innovation contest to large enterprises as beneficiaries, and involving startups as solvers • Startup incubators and accelerators, using innovation contests to engage startups with larger enterprises

- Development agencies such as European Enterprise Network contact points, most likely in partnerships with universities, or with open innovation intermediaries in the market.

5. How do you think as a consortium we could **facilitate and accelerate the adoption** of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?

- Manage the final event for the best
- Launch and facilitate an european network of innovation agencies exchanging practices and know-how with regards on designing and managing innovations contests and other research-industry open innovation schemes for SMEs
- This should be supported by EU funding, e.g. HORIZON-EIE-CONNECT-02: Preparatory action for setting up joint programmes among innovation ecosystems actors (European Innovation Ecosystem, Pillar III, Horizon EU)
- Research should also be funded to demonstrate the impact of open innovation contests in fostering innovation in SMEs, especially for breaking the barriers between SMEs and academia in open innovation processes

3 A Cross-cutting summary of pilot outcomes.

3.1 Added value for SMEs

The UX Challenge brings about positive results and impacts on participating companies at different levels, which are normally evaluated separately, by means of qualitative methodology (one on one interviews after a few weeks from the end of the initiative): 1) outputs: what the companies can practically bring home from the initiative, from a tangible standpoint; 2) other results: less tangible value-adding results that the companies can gain by participating in the Challenge; 3) outcomes: follow up activities that the company decides to launch in the short to medium term as a direct result of the participation in the Challenge; 4) impacts: medium to long term positive benefits experienced by the company as a direct or indirect outcome from participating in the UX Challenge.

Here are some suggestive evidences about the benefits normally produced by the UX Challenge in companies, across the 4 evaluation dimensions.

3.1.1 Actionable outputs

Companies participating in the UX Challenge are usually very impressed by the outputs delivered by the solvers, in terms of novelty and maturation (implementation readiness), also in the light of the short time available.

All outputs are tangible (not just “ideas”) and fully exploitable by companies (IPR is owned the them). But, what outputs are we talking about, ultimately? The UX Challenge delivers three strands of outputs to the beneficiary companies:

- App and software interface prototypes with different degrees of maturation:
 - interface mockups and sketches, focussing on high-level feature. Developed on paper, whiteboards, or Google Slides / Powerpoint.
 - interface wireframes and mid-level prototypes, focussing on information architecture and user flows, with low graphic details. Developed on prototyping software such as Balsamiq, Marvel, or just Google Slides.
 - testable prototypes, with clear links between screens, detailed user flow, graphical details, and some copy. Developed on prototyping software such as Sketch, Figma, Adobe Xd.
- Results from user testing, in terms of user feedback on prototypes (or as-is version of product), and insights for improvement (both at usability level and utility / value proposition level). This comes in the form of text quotes or field data, e.g. interview audio or video recording.
- Guidelines for improvement of the overall design, developed by the solvers, on top of the previous outputs: these are more consultancy-level insights impacting on the product development process as a whole.

3.1.2 Other results

Apart from the outputs, the UX Challenge allows participating companies to bring home other less tangible though very relevant direct results, which can be fully implemented. These are such as:

- Talent scouting: solvers are young bright mind willing to make the extra mile to excel in the same technology or business field as the benefiting companies.
- Improved networking with potential partners: mentors are usually experienced professionals that may act as product development and innovation partners to the benefiting companies. Other beneficiary companies may also act as potential business partners, co-innovators, or even customers.
- Improved knowledge, know-how and awareness of benefits of innovation methodologies, such as the design sprint, design thinking, user-centred design, and, technology user-testing, especially.

3.1.3 Promising follow-up outcomes

Apart from the outputs and the other results that companies gain from the UX Challenge, what happens next? There are many outcomes and follow up activities that normally companies do as a results of participating to a UX Challenge

- Industrialization of the challenge outputs into a market-ready version, and their industrialization within new or improved products and services. This is the most impactful outcome, and happens rarely, as it requires very mature outputs, but especially, it requires full alignment between the challenge timeline and the product development process, which is hard to achieve, and risk-prone for the company.
- Further maturation of the outputs, possibly by means of additional design sprints, with to achieve future industrialization, or further assess feasibility. This can happen in a variety of ways: by the company's personnell alone; with the involvement of the team of solvers (or part of it), who may also be awarded additional prizes or incentives given by the company; hiring one or more solvers with a short-term project contract, or within an internship; with the involvement of one mentor (a freelance UX designer, a Design firm, a HCI researcher or professor). In this final case, a formal R&D collaboration is established between the company and one product development partner. This is possibly the most fruitful outcome, as the scope of such collaboration normally spans well beyond the scope of the challenge, and can impact on the company business as a whole.
- Solvers can be invited to make a presentation about the outputs at the company premises, with a larger audience, with the aim of creating momentum for initiating a product innovation process.

3.1.4 Long-term impacts

Apart from the outputs, results and outcomes, participating in the UX Challenge brings about medium to long-term impacts in the company business, such as the following.

- Increased knowledge of user centred design, UX design and usability methodologies, including the design sprint; increased awareness of the benefits of such methodologies, as well as open innovation in general; increased know-how about how to implement these methodologies in practice. All these impacts on the capacity of design advocates within the company to make the case for the need to start adopting UCD, and to create momentum for change within the company. This impact is based on the capability of the UX Challenge to make available evidence that support company decision making at the management level. Often, these evidence are used to consolidate already existing business hypotheses.
- Adoption of UCD methods in projects other than one subject to the Challenge, possibly with innovation partners beyond the solvers or mentors from the Challenge. This is most common for usability testing, and user research, which can be purchased in the market and applied to all kind of products and services, and development projects.
- Based on the previous, one company may decide to take up more structural changes, such as hiring a UX designer, and/or creating a design team within the company (in case of medium-sized enterprises). This will have a major impact with regards of the capability to implement UCD in future projects.

3.2 Internal retrospective of the pilot

This section collects the results of an internal retrospective that project partners carried out together during an internal workshop, based on the experience obtained during the different implementation of the Challenges in each country. This sub-section is divided in 3 subtopics:

- things that went well.
- things that went less well.
- general suggestions.

The retrospective was facilitated by HIT by means of a Miro board. Results of the retrospective are included below and represented the basis to develop insight to improve and scale up the UX Challenge scheme.

Figure 3.1: screenshot from workshop #1.1 Miro board.

3.2.1 Things that went well

We can classify the topics as follows:

Technical aspects

Different tools were used in the different participants' locations: Miro, Slack, Zoom, etc. and they provided good mechanisms to foster collaborations among all the solvers and testers together with the correspondent mentors in a co-creation approach. Videoconference tools such as Zoom permitted an efficient online interaction among all the team members during the pandemic situation of COVID-19.

Methodology

The Design Sprint method used in the different UX Challenges was very useful to address co-creation processes with multidisciplinary teams such in this Usability Challenge. Using the Design Sprint strengthen the creativity process among all the students involved prototyping co-created ideas.

Soft skills

On the other hand, one of the most important skills acquired by the solvers, testers and mentors in the different participant's locations are the soft skills: team working, problem solving, leadership, cooperativeness, communication skills, etc.

3.2.2 Things that went less well

Some common comments brought up by most of the partners as a weaknesses of the process were related to the randomized selection of the companies taking part in the UX Challenges, due to the RCT - Randomized Control Trial study design in which the UX Challenge treatment was embedded process: on one side, it was not possible to select the best companies with highest scores; on the other, many companies that were not selected did not understand the reason behind a random selection, and felt frustrated. This can potentially compromise the relations between an innovation agency and the companies in its ecosystem.

Other aspect was the company outreach, which was a difficult process. In some cases, the company outreach capacity by some project partners was rather low. This could be done by lack of marketing and communication skills in project partners, as well as a general unawareness of terms like UX Design, Design Sprint, UX Challenge, hackathon and open innovation opportunities. To recruit all 194 participating companies, overall, has been a very demanding job. However, normally a UX Challenge would support between 5 and 10 companies at time. We believe any innovation agency should not face issues in reaching out and selecting such amount of beneficiary SMEs.

Some partners consider that more training of the sprint would be needed for both solvers and SMEs, and some deeper introduction to UX Challenge concept.

During the execution of the Challenges, in some cases, the lack of breaks during daily operations was an added problem and the big effort done by at the end of the day produces “brain dead” in the participants.

Other issues were related with the follow-up surveys that the companies involved in the UX Challenge had to fill in, as part of the RCT study design: especially, control group companies saw no incentive in filling in the follow up survey.

3.2.3 Suggestions for improving the UX Challenge scheme

Below we include some suggestions for improving the UX Challenge scheme were proposed by the partners.

Regarding the prizes:

- It is really difficult to justify prizes, because teams work with different companies and not all of the companies have the same skills and grade of commitment, so it will be better give a general prize and do not make differences.
- Give a reason why the winners won the challenge. Spend time on an explanation
- Prizes given out by companies, more motivation for participants and support for recruiting of Solvers (Tehnopol)

The international side had to be more strengthened:

- International setting was not leveraged (HIT)

- Exploit the international setting more: Organize an international / joint UX Challenge, mix participants from different countries. This could further improve the appeal to participants (Stanbeis Europa Zentrum)

Other suggestions that were provided entailed to strengthen communication with all parties involved (starting with local partners, continuing with the UX Challenge participants, and finishing with the communication and organisation of the final event). Also, it is crucial to test technical aspects of the UX Challenge operations and final event with different possible scenarios that may occur during the real event.

3.3 How to further exploit the UX Challenge

Once the retrospective was completed, a second internal workshop was conducted to develop ideas on how to evolve the UX Challenge scheme, and scale it up to other domains. These insights were developed during an internal half-day workshop involving all seven project partners that piloted the UX Challenges in seven countries. The workshop was facilitated by HIT in a way similar to a focus group, with a number of questions posed to all participants, plus short sharing and discussion sessions facilitated on a Miro board (https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_IHL_WKo=/).

The discussion topics were the following:

1. Do you think your organization may decide to **run again** the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?
2. What would be the **key tips** you'd give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?
3. Do you think it could be possible to **adapt the UX Challenge** format to support innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?
4. What **type of Innovation Agencies** (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may actually be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?
5. How do you think a as a consortium **we could facilitate** and accelerate the adoption of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?

Figure 3.2: screenshot from workshop #1.2 Miro board.

3.3.1 Future replication

Project partners were first asked if they consider running again the UX Challenge in the future. In particular, the question asked was: “Do you think your organization may decide to run again the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) in the future? Why?”. Below we present the clustered results from this first discussion, which are very promising, by making available the very same words from project partners.

- Yes.
 - We have been running the UX Challenge since 2017, and we’ll keep on organizing it in the future, maybe with some **changes** in the format (e.g. duration, preparatory activities, integration with relevant university courses) (HIT).
 - Run a new UX Challenge. In fact, we are considering new dates to do a new UX Challenge with the SME that did not participate in this edition. Most likely, in September 2021 we will run another UX hackathon (ESP).
 - We plan to integrate the UX Challenge with university master courses on Human Computer Interaction to make it easier to select solvers and manage operations (HIT).
- YEs, with external funding.
 - With funding: After seeing the result (3 companies have decided to adapt the solution from the UX Challenge to their products) we might consider offering the UX Challenge-like initiatives in the future. However, to do that we would need to attract additional funding as the organisation of the initiative requires financial, human and time resources

- that we do not have outside of the scope of 200SMEchallenge project (LIC).
- However, the precondition would be to have the right cooperation partners and to find financing for it. Generally, the format was very beneficial to our organization in terms of outreach to companies, company support, marketing, synergies between sectors (SIG).
 - Yes, as the value for the participants - both companies and Solvers - got proven and based on the feedback of companies and Mentors, there clearly is need in the market for UX-related services and awareness. The aspect that needs sorting out prior to that is the financing part - who will pay for the organisation of that? (THP).
 - If we have a suitable project and some money. Hopefully we can hold a next event after summertime. Feedback was so positive. Design Sprints / UX Challenges will be a part of the Innovation Services in Business Oulu (BO).
- Unclear
 - The UX Challenge worked very well. It provided students with experience, and companies with value. Solvers were able to bring in new knowledge, methodologies, and tools to the table. An initiative/method we should continue working with, also with different focus areas (not just UX) (DDC).

3.3.2 Tips and suggestion for implementation of the UX Challenge

During the internal workshop, secondly, we wanted to extract key tips and hints on how to implement the UX Challenge, that could be shared with other innovation agencies willing to replicate the scheme. Partners were asked the following: “What would be the key tips you’d give to another innovation agency willing to run the UX Challenge?” Again, we provide the outcomes of the discussion in a clustered fashion, keeping track of the source.

1. Planning.
 - a. Look for sponsors to get valuable prizes for the winners and other participants.
 - b. Find partners that can help to attract solvers, testers and mentors to the event (e.g. university, business representative associations).
 - c. Consider to host the Challenge in more than 2 days to allow solvers and companies to better work on ideation and prototyping and get to more mature results. Fixed costs / effort will not change, but the impact will be much higher.
 - d. Don’t recruit students only as Solvers but other design and UX enthusiasts as well.
 - e. Consider virtual setting since this increases your potential participant number.
 - f. Personnel: plan manpower (staff with expertise and supporting staff for organizational matters).
2. Promotion.
 - a. Manage the launch and promotion as you would launch an innovative product into the market: design a marketing funnel based on a stage-gate approach; manage the single applications and act on them with promo and communication actions to have them convert from prospects, to leads to customers.
 - b. Leverage on partners’ channels to promote the initiative.
 - c. Make sure to select companies and solvers are committed to the initiative: dropouts from solvers and especially lack of commitment from companies can hinder the good execution

of the Challenge.

3. Preparation.

- a. All participants (solvers, companies, mentors) must precisely be instructed on how the UX Challenge will take place, and what they have to do, in the various phases of the challenge, in order to avoid loss of time and miscoordination.
- b. Invest as much as possible in preparatory activities with solvers (training on the design sprint, meeting with mentors, ice breaking and team building activities). Providing a short training on the design sprint to companies too may be beneficial.
- c. Make sure teams meet each other prior to the UX Challenge to ensure good chemistry and understanding of each other's skills.
- d. Provide teams with good software, even if this means paying for it - this allows the result to be as good as possible.
- e. Invest as much as possible in preparatory activities with companies (creating a shared challenge brief document for clarifying the challenge, its constraints, the goal of the sprint, and the expected outputs).
- f. Getting the product ready for the challenge: it needs to be accessible and testable by solvers and testers.
- g. Briefing the mentors about the process and the companies and challenges selected in the initiative.
- h. Preparing the Miro boards, which needs to incorporate the template for the sprint activities: these serve as a blueprint for the teams' operations.

4. Execution.

- a. Increase the number of Testers and user testing interviews, if possible - that is the most valuable part in the process.
- b. Make sure to avoid technical issues, especially if event is organised online. Test as much as possible platforms and especially their switches to live events on social media platforms in order to avoid misunderstandings and time breaks. It is good to bring third party people to test breakout rooms, ability to share documents etc.
- c. Monitoring progress and implementation with both solvers, mentors and companies to identify possible issues, especially in the beginning of the sprint (phase 1: Map the problem).
- d. Give enough space for presenting the results, both to solvers and companies: the final event should be the celebration of a successful initiative and the value it provides to all participants.
- e. If possible, run the event as physical event to allow socializing and networking as an additional value of the event.

5. Follow up.

- a. Provide certificates to the solvers as they would like to add them to their portfolios.
- b. Informal phone calls with participating companies to evaluate satisfaction and outcomes.
- c. Use the same evaluation method across years to compare results.

3.3.3 Adaptation to other scopes

After that, partners discussed on how to possibly scale up the UX Challenge scheme to other domains. The question was: *“Do you think it could be possible to adapt the UX Challenge format to support*

innovation in other types of SMEs (beyond digital) by means of other innovation methodologies (e.g. beyond the Design Sprint) and other solvers and mentors?”. Results follow:

- Yes: starting from the UX Challenge format, we have designed other two Innovation Challenges: one with the aim to accelerate the adoption of Additive Manufacturing in SMEs; another with the aim to accelerate the adoption of Artificial Intelligence solutions in manufacturing SMEs. They both have longer time spans than the UX Challenge (about 3 months). However, the working model is very similar: what changes is basically the problem-solving activities, and the profile of companies and solvers (HIT).
- In the future we might decide to activate other Innovation Challenges in the domain of biotechnologies (HIT).
- All SMEs need improvements and new learning processes to be adapted to the present, so a UX Challenge is necessary in a lot of companies, regardless of the sector or the degree of innovation, because in a UX Challenge you can use different perspectives and disciplines to help your company. Besides, several people working together can get really good results (ESP).
- Design sprint can be applied beyond digital challenges. It could be very useful for some social challenges, for NGO sector and social enterprises. We received several requests from NGO and even public sector (like public companies) and had to decline them even though their challenge would be perfect with the design sprint methodology (LIC, SIG).
- I see this as a problem-solving methodology and the problem can be anything else than a digital product or service. I think this methodology is very adaptable to different problems, industries and company types (THP).
- Adapted Design Sprint is also suitable for other than digital cases (BO, DDC, SIG).

3.3.4 Innovation Agencies possibly interested

After that, the discussion focussed on what kind of innovation agencies could be interested in adopting the UX Challenge scheme. The workshop question was: *“What type of Innovation Agencies (or players, in general, including business and education organizations) do you think may actually be interested in activating and running the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative)?”*. This discussion was set the stage to the organization of a second workshop having consultation purposes, with external innovation agencies which could be the recipient of the new scheme (see next section). Again, results are hereby reported in a clustered way.

- Intermediaries.
 - Universities, through teams and initiatives aiming at supporting innovation and education in entrepreneurship: Contamination Labs, technology transfer offices. Especially, those providing technical skills to future UI/UX specialists.
 - Technology transfer organizations and university innovation centres, as-a-service.

- Startup incubators and accelerators, using innovation contests to engage startups with larger enterprises.
 - Public Innovation Agencies and Development agencies such as European Enterprise Network contact points, most likely in partnerships with universities, or with open innovation intermediaries in the market.
 - Business support organizations (chambers of commerce, local and regional business support).
 - Industry clusters, business representative associations.
 - Digital Innovation Hubs.
 - NGO sector.
 - Open Innovation service providers in the market: offering the innovation contest to large enterprises as beneficiaries, and involving startups as solvers.
- End users (Seekers).
 - Companies, in general, beyond SMEs.
 - Companies, especially in the digital / ICT sector.
 - Companies in the digital media sector.
 - Companies in the tourism sector.
 - Companies in the transportation sector.

3.3.5 How to accelerate adoption and mainstreaming

Finally, the discussion focusses on how the consortium could foster the adoption of the piloted UX Challenge scheme. The question was: *“How do you think a as a consortium we could facilitate and accelerate the adoption of the UX Challenge (or a similar initiative) across Europe?”*. Results are the following.

- Manage the final event for the best (HIT).
- Launch and facilitate an European network of innovation agencies exchanging practices and know-how with regards on designing and managing innovations contests and other research-industry open innovation schemes for SMEs (HIT).
- This should be supported by EU funding, e.g. HORIZON-EIE-CONNECT-02: *Preparatory action for setting up joint programmes among innovation ecosystems actors* (European Innovation Ecosystem, Pillar III, Horizon EU) (HIT).
- Research should also be funded to demonstrate the impact of open innovation contests in fostering innovation in SMEs, especially for breaking the barriers between SMEs and academia in open innovation processes (HIT).
- Organizing more often, National UX Hackatons, such as 200SMEchallenge project has led, and encouraging universities and design schools to participate. Other options are cross-country UX

Hackatons, providing different set of solvers from different countries to companies in order to ensure the penetration on other European markets.

- Engage with Innovation agencies possibly interested in the topic (LIC).
- Demonstrate the benefits of the event by using the feedback from solvers and companies while presenting the UX Challenge (LIC).
- Think about the international scope of the UX Challenge, for challenges, solvers, mentors, testers (maybe it could be organised as a multinational event instead of region-based (LIC).
- Disseminate project results: results of study will be relevant to prove that this kind of format brings benefits to companies and/ or students (SIG).
- With our hands-on experience we could act as advisors to those who plan to run the initiative for the first time (THP).
- Learn from mistakes and share “what not to do” - this is just as valuable as knowing “what to do” (DDC).

4 Consultation of external innovation agencies

4.1 The Stakeholders' Scheme Scale-up Workshop

This section features insights developed within a third, larger, workshop organized by project partners, with the aim of supporting the future uptake of the UX Challenge scheme: *Stakeholders' Scheme Scale-up Workshop*.

The workshop involved a circle of external innovation agencies interested in the scheme, possibly acting as a community of future early adopters. Innovation agencies were outreached and invited by project partners at a national level depending on their role of influencers in the SME policy landscape. They were invited in commenting the outcome of the experimentation and providing requirements and conditions for a wider utilization of the piloted scheme. Fourteen innovation agencies were invited and participated, as per the project plan.

Notice that the workshop was initially planned to take place in Tallinn (EE), but due to the COVID-19 surge was held online. Follows a report and main highlights from these workshops.

4.1.1 Workshop planning and participants

The interactive part of the workshop was anticipated by a presentation of the project and the UX Challenge (by HIT), as well as of the ongoing results of the trial (by FBK). Also, a Project Officer from the European Commission was invited to participate as a speaker.

Agenda

9:30 – 10:00 Project 200SMEchallenge and ongoing results

10:00 – 10:30 Eric Koch, EISMEA (former EASME) Opportunities for Innovation Agencies in Horizon Europe Pillar III + Q&A

10:30 – 11:15 Group breakout sessions to foresee continuation and future collaborations

11:15 – 12:00 Debrief of breakout sessions and discussion

Panel discussion: participants were divided into a number of groups and discussion was facilitated by project partners, after a short presentation round table. The discussion and elicitation of feedback among participating innovation agencies was facilitated via the following three topics:

1. How did you **understand** the main concept of the UX Challenge? What part are you more interested in? (facilitator can provide further explanation and Q&A)
2. Do you have any **experience** of running innovation contests? How would you compare it/them to the UX Challenge?
3. How you think you might be **interested** in running an innovation contest? At what conditions? (targeted companies and challenges, partners, funding, ...).

Each group utilized a separated Miro board, as follows:

Figure 3.3: screenshot from workshop #2 Miro board.

Below we provide the list of the participating Innovation Agencies, matched with the group they joined, facilitated by one project partner.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824212.

Project contact	Innovation Agency	Type	Discussion panel (facilitator)
HIT	University of Trento	University	A. Universities (Kadi)
HIT	Miskolc University	University	A. Universities (Kadi)
HIT	University of Oulu	University	A. Universities (Kadi)
LIC	Vilnius Gediminas technical university	University	A. Universities (Kadi)
LIC	Autonomous University of Barcelona	University	A. Universities (Kadi)
Steinbeis	University of Applied Science Karlsruhe/ department entrepreneurship	University	A. Universities (Kadi)
Technopol	Mainor	Development authority	A. Universities (Kadi)
	Españtec (HOST)	Science Park	A. Universities (Kadi)
	Hub Innovazione Trentino #2 (HOST)	Innovation & tech Transfer	A. Universities (Kadi)
	Technopol (HOST)	Science Park	A. Universities (Kadi)
HIT	Bay Zoltan	RTO	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
HIT	BGI	RTO	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
HIT	FFG	National research support agency	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
HIT	Miskolc University	University	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
LIC	Agency for Science, Innovation and Technology (MITA)	Governmental Agency	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
Business Oulu	Oulu University Innovation Centre	University TTO	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
	Hub Innovazione Trentino (HOST)	Tech transfer agency	B. RTO & tech transfer (Nicola)
HIT	University of Trento	University	C. Science parks (Juan)
Españtec	Valladolid Scientific and	Science park	C. Science parks (Juan)

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	Technological park		
Espatec	Spanish Association of Scientific and Technological parks	Science park	C. Science parks (Juan)
Technopol	Tartu Science Park	Science park	D. Social Innovation agencies (Miriam)
Technopol	Tartu Science Park	Science park	C. Science parks (Juan)
Steinbeis	Friuli Innovazione (Udine)	Science park and innovation	C. Science parks (Juan)
Technopol	Tartu Science Park	Science park	C. Science parks (Juan)
	Espatec (HOST)	Science Park	C. Science parks (Juan)
HIT	Ecoplus	Business Agency	D. Social Innovation agencies (Miriam)
Steinbeis	Kozjansko Innovation	Development Agency	C. Science parks (Juan)
Steinbeis	Center Noordung	Innovation agency	D. Social Innovation agencies (Miriam)
Steinbeis	Croatian Chamber of Economy	Chamber of Commerce	D. Social Innovation agencies (Miriam)
Steinbeis	Fomento San Sebastian	Development Agency/ business support	D. Social Innovation agencies (Miriam)
	Steinbeis (HOST)	Development authority	D. Social Innovation agencies (Miriam)
Steinbeis	Barco/ researcher	Corporate/ research on hackathons in companies	E. Business dev and clusters #1 (Vitalija)
Business Oulu	Business Tampere, The economic development agency of Tampere region	Development authority	E. Business dev and clusters #1 (Vitalija)
	Lithuanian Innovation Centre (HOST)	Innovation agency	E. Business dev and clusters #1 (Vitalija)
Espatec	Castellón Chamber Commerce.	Chamber of commerce	E. Business dev and clusters #1 (Vitalija)
HIT	Asociación de la Industria Navarra	Industry Cluster	F. Business dev and clusters #2 (Elisa)
HIT	BWcon	Industry cluster	F. Business dev and clusters #2

			(Elisa)
HIT	Innosquare	Development Agency	F. Business dev and clusters #2 (Elisa)
LIC	Vidzeme Vidzeme Planning Region	Regional development authority	F. Business dev and clusters #2 (Elisa)
Business Oulu	Turku Business Region (Regional Development Company)	Development authority	F. Business dev and clusters #2 (Elisa)
	Hub Innovazione Trentino #2 (HOST)	Innovation & tech Transfer	F. Business dev and clusters #2 (Elisa)
Steinbeis	Stadt Aalen - Department of Business Support	Local authority/ Business Support	G. Business dev and clusters #3 (Hannu)
HIT	KEPA	Innovation agency for design	G. Business dev and clusters #3 (Hannu)
Espaitec	Castellón Chamber Commerce.	Chamber of commerce	G. Business dev and clusters #3 (Hannu)
	Business Oulu (HOST)	Business agency	G. Business dev and clusters #3 (Hannu)
Steinbeis	UP Designstudio Studio	design company	H. Design players (Emma)
Technopol	Estonian Academy of Arts	University	H. Design players (Emma)
HIT	KEPA	Innovation agency for design	H. Design players (Emma)
	Danish Design Centre (HOST)	Innovation agency for design	H. Design players (Emma)

Table 3.1: List of participants of the Stakeholders Scheme Scaleup Workshop.

4.1.2 Workshop outcomes

The workshop involved about 40 participants beyond the organizers, from 14 innovation agencies. We report here below all the contributions that were collected from the participants on the three questions. We report these “raw data” to allow for future interpretations. However, the contributions were clustered into common themes that will be considered to identify hot topics around which possibly launching collaboration opportunities. Between parentheses we specify the affiliation of the contributor: Uni = university; RTO = research and technology organization; Park = Scientific park; Soc = social innovation actor; Dev = business development and/or innovation agency.

Group A: Universities

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1. **How did you understand the main concept of the UX Challenge? What part are you more interested in?**
 - a. OI contests and UX Challenge effective tools to support new product development in SMEs (apart from technology innovation).
 - i. Mixing different professional profiles working with the design sprint methodology, to design new digital products. The most interesting part to me is how you make it tangible afterwards, moving from the practical exercise to the "real" world (Soc).
 - ii. The submitted challenge can be in different stages of new product development (also already on the market) (Uni).
 - iii. The differences stemming from receiving an integrated service as opposed to no or limited service (Soc).
 - iv. Different sectors can apply (Dev).
 - b. OI contests and UX Challenge as effective tools to support open Innovation, especially involving high tech and research partners.
 - i. The Challenge provider are the SMEs (Uni).
 - ii. The innovation work is supported by mentors and a feedback for improvement is provided by testers; possibility to "pilot" ideas with experts (Uni).
 - iii. Most interesting is the SME support element and the challenge-based element (i.e. answering a challenge as integral part of the scheme) (RTO).
 - iv. interesting the open innovation approach and the boosting of SMEs knowledge associated (RTO).
 - v. The most interesting aspect of the programme is the scheme or common methodology and collaboration between SMEs and Universities (Park).
 - vi. A good way for SMEs to attract talent and develop innovative products (Park).
 - vii. The process is really inspiring and needed for boosting innovation (Dev).
 - viii. key success factors: SME join with a real need (Park).
 - c. Interest in operational aspects, such as motivations and incentives.
 - i. Motivation for students, profit for SMEs (Park).
 - ii. Contact with SME: appreciated by university students (Park).
 - iii. Involvement of solvers/students with predefined background (Park).
 - d. Education impact and other impacts on students.
 - i. Not only a case study but a real problem case from companies (Uni).
 - ii. It allows interactive and dynamic learning for students and SMEs (pedagogical aspects for the "learners") (Uni).
 - iii. It is a good programme to provide job opportunities for students (Park).
 - iv. The innovation needs and the learning needs from solvers can differ (Uni).
 - e. Interest in the RCT - Randomized Control Trial method.
 - i. The evaluation of impact can be done with RCT (Uni).
 - ii. interested in knowing more about the RCT methodology (Uni).
 - f. Interest in design, design thinking, co-creation, UX and usability.
 - i. The Design Sprint is what's most important (Uni).
 - ii. In some what familiar with UX Challenge concept; most interested of the GV Sprint model (Uni, business development).
 - iii. Use some digital products to see the usability by some solvers (Park).

- iv. very specific profile wanted: design background (Park).
- v. available testing users provided (Park).
- vi. Diverging and converging with different ppl with different backgrounds towards building solutions (Soc).
- vii. Solvers (students) is very interesting point (Park).
- viii. Engage students and companies. Use techniques of cocreation (Park).
- ix. design sprint = a methodology that can be applied on a broad set of contexts (Park).

2. Do you have any experience of running innovation contests? How would you compare it/them to the UX Challenge?

- a. Experience with existing innovation contests challenge such as hackathons
 - i. Previous experience in running hackathons (multidisciplinary teams); difficulties in running trainings before the challenge due to large dropouts (Soc).
 - ii. Innovation contest in additive manufacturing (RTO).
 - iii. We launch Innovation city challenges, mixing students with companies and Tech centres. Students have to design and develop innovative solutions for the cities including one disruptive technology, helped with the mentorship of those local companies. We also launch innovation challenges to help startups develop innovative products/services, in different fields such as health, etc. This year we will do it in the AI field (Soc).
- b. Closeness with startup and entrepreneurship programs, or similar.
 - i. experience with hackatons, calls, pitches, young innovators contest, accelerators (Uni).
 - ii. EUAS (Estonian Entrepreneurship University of Applied Sciences) students are participating in StarterTallinn and GlobalGameJam, those are not contests, but related to innovation (Uni).
 - iii. responsible for pre-incubator program in Oulu before. And in the University context I have run our joint accelerator program with the University of Applied Sciences Oulu (as a part of Uni Oulu Business School Entrepreneurship minor studies). I have also facilitated several sprints and hackathons. Alongside my work I am a SD Master's student in Uni Lapland (Uni, Business dev).
 - iv. Not exactly, I have experience in running a cascade funding based support scheme for SMEs in need of innovative technology solutions (in Hungary and in the surrounding areas) and my colleagues are running challenge-based contests for students to popularise science (RTO).

3. How you think you might be interested in running an innovation contest? At what conditions? (targeted companies and challenges, partners, funding, ...)

- a. Repeat the UX Challenge or other current experiences, or adapt it.
 - i. Espaitec is interested in running innovation contest, and our experience with 200SME is so good that we are going to have more hackathons (Park).
 - ii. will continue run innovation contests; we will get inspiration from UX Challenge (Park).
 - iii. Keep the challenge at regional level (Dev).

- iv. Adapt the UX Challenge for out Innovation Center in Cooperation with our SMEs (Dev).
- v. Scale at the international level (Dev).
- b. Scaling up to researchers as solvers.
 - i. we might be interested in running a program for our researchers. We have models for this already but haven't done them in couple of years (Uni).
 - ii. open innovation programs connecting teams of researchers with companies to exploit existing know- how and IP (RTO).
- c. Innovation contests in other technology verticals / industry.
 - i. innovation contest on industrial Artificial Intelligence (RTO).
 - ii. Yes, but with different scope, involving experts (Uni).
 - iii. We would like to get in innovation contests such as AI and companies, city challenges faced through AI and local entities for example, or Big Data related challenges (Soc).
 - iv. Challenge in the social innovation realm (Uni).
- d. Building capacity in Innovation Agencies and addressing feasibility issues.
 - i. building capacity in other innovation agencies and universities to design tailored innovation contests (RTO).
 - ii. Interested in running innovation contest and for us it is important to desing a good common methodology and sponsors/ prizes to attract the more possible participants (Association of Scientific Parks).
 - iii. more staff is needed to run such a project (Soc).
- e. Radically change the format, involving new stakeholders.
 - i. New perspective, cascade funding, or private equity (Dev).
 - ii. Follow up opportunities using regional tools, e.g. employment services (Dev).

4.2 Promising avenues for future developments of the scheme

Under the light of the above emerged topics of interest, we list here below a number of avenues for future collaboration and scale of the UX Challenge.

1. **Building capacity on Open Innovation programs.** Open innovation programs such as innovation contests are recognized to be rather complicated to design and manage, and many players recognize the option of receiving training. To design and run innovation contests requires skills and know-how should be shared and transferred from more experience players to less experienced ones. Peer learning and capacity building among innovation agencies should be facilitated. Especially universities may benefit from this since they may not have the right skills and personnel to run innovation contests. A very effective tool is available to drive support and coaching programs: the Innovation Challenge Design Canvas, developed by INNOSUP-05 project INNOCHALLENGE¹.
2. **Adaptation and tuning of the UX Challenge.** Exporting the UX Challenge model, or similar (other open innovation contests) to other enabling technologies or industry. This is already happening,

¹ <https://www.innochallenge-project.eu/>.

e.g. having RTOs and Innovation Agencies running innovation contests on topics such as Additive Manufacturing or Artificial intelligence. This entails that innovation agencies should embark in a process of analysis of the contexts, adaptation of the format, creation of critical mass locally, piloting a first edition of a newly designed open innovation contest.

3. **Liaison with startup programs.** Open Innovation is often perceived as something that regards startups (who can act as “solvers” to challenges provided by larger enterprises). Similarly, many Innovation Agencies think of innovation contests and hackathons as tools that are linked to startup incubation and acceleration programs. To consider startups as beneficiaries of innovation contests (also in the form of mentors) could be a way to explore other funding opportunities beyond those related to SME innovation support and/or technology transfer.
4. **Scale the format to new stakeholders.** There is an interest in exploring the application of these open innovation contests to other players, e.g. involving researchers as solvers, with the aim to pursue technology transfer goals (tech-driven open innovation). This is of course challenging, as the motivational levers and incentives may be harder to find. This could match with involvement of funding players, with making available funding for the designed innovation stemming from the new program format. Buy-in from all stakeholders should be ensured.
5. **Bring design thinking in SMEs.** There is an interest in design thinking methodologies, including the Design Sprint, and other user-centred design methods. They are perceived as effective and innovative approaches for supporting product development and innovation in SMEs: however, they are not as diffused as project partners though they would be. Innovation agencies as well as SMEs should be more exposed to these methodologies, in order to increase their knowledge about them, and related benefits.

